

MAKING RESEARCH WORK FOR YOU

A good practice
guide to qualitative
research in
consultancy

WHAT IS QUALITATIVE RESEARCH?

Qualitative research involves collecting and analysing non-numerical data, such as interview notes, transcription, video or audio, to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences.

In practice, this means exploring how people perceive or understand a trend, event, or intervention. The insights gained from this process can then be used to inform organisational strategy and decision-making, sometimes in combination with quantitative data.

Qualitative research can be tailored to almost any requirement or research question and is an extremely flexible approach. It can be seen as a toolbox of different ways to engage and understand your stakeholders.

Thinking beyond the words and figures: qualitative research forms a detailed picture of people's views, positions and motivations.

 One-to-one interviews offer real-time interaction, conversation and reaction

 Case studies provide an in-depth, real life understanding of complex issues

 Focus groups generate valuable lived-experience data for us to examine

 Open-ended surveys let respondents share their views in their own words

BENEFITS OF QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

Qualitative research is our tool of choice when we help clients form a detailed understanding of their stakeholders' views and feelings.

It will benefit you by:

- Providing a nuanced understanding of stakeholders' views, positions and motivations that is unlikely to emerge from quantitative data alone.
- Generating unanticipated insights to highlight gaps and reflect lived experiences.
- Highlighting similarities and differences across different stakeholder groups and/or segments, such as age, gender or seniority.
- Generating results that are accessible and suitable for broader communications and marketing activities.
- Being highly flexible and adaptable to your specific requirements.

OUR TOP TIPS

When you deliver a qualitative research project, you need to balance a number of considerations.

1 / HAVE A CLEAR GOAL

Before getting started, make sure you know exactly what you want to find out.

2 / MANAGE EXPECTATIONS

Create and send out a briefing note, so everyone knows what to expect when contributing.

3 / ASK OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS

Identify clear, neutral, open-ended questions and be ready to probe deeper.

4 / PLAN CAREFULLY

Plan your time and costs every step of the way, so you can stick to your timeline.

5 / THANK CONTRIBUTORS

Write to your contributors to thank them and share any public outputs with them.

QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN USE

OPINIONS, ATTITUDES AND MOTIVATIONS ON A NETWORK OF RESEARCH CENTRES

A leading Asian research funder wished to understand their reputation among foreign academics, building on the activities of a network of internationally-focused research centres they fund.

We were asked to undertake an interview campaign which attracted responses from 66 stakeholders, comprising 55 academics, three editors and eight policy-makers and funders. The interviewees covered a wide range of countries and institutions. The survey aimed to understand the contributors' viewpoints and experiences and enable the research centres to continue to adapt to a rapidly-changing research environment.

We found that interviewees were overwhelmingly positive about the research centres but through their feedback we were able to highlight some areas for improvement.

LIBRARIANS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS OPEN ACCESS

We interviewed librarians from 17 organisations across Asia, Europe and North America, aiming to better understand the potential impact of a shift to open access in a publisher's top journal portfolio.

Our main objectives were to investigate: (i) the value of the portfolio to institutional libraries; (ii) the impact of future open access scenarios on subscription and decision-making; and (iii) the relative importance of primary research versus other types of content, such as editorials or letters.

We provided our client, a leading publisher, with stakeholder views and insights to inform their strategic decision-making on pricing and open access activities.

QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN USE

UNDERSTANDING INNOVATION IN RESEARCH REPRODUCIBILITY

We engaged over 50 stakeholders from 12 different countries to explore current practices and barriers in the area of research reproducibility.

Our findings sought to compare and inspire strategies, policies and operational practice and share lessons learned from a range of stakeholder groups. Using interviews and focus groups, we heard the views of research funding organisations, research performing organisations, learned societies, researchers, academic publishers and infrastructure and service providers.

By combining our research findings with an extensive literature review, we produced a final report discussing reproducible publication practices as part of a broad process of cultural and technical change in the research landscape.

THE ROLE OF HYBRID OPEN ACCESS IN EXTENDING AUTHOR CHOICE

We interviewed 33 authors of gold open access articles to understand their motivations and influencing factors when selecting the hybrid open access option.

Via thematic coding, we were able to distinguish three types of authors in terms of their attitude to open access – supporters, opportunists and those disinterested in its use.

Our research found that the most important factor for researchers when deciding where to publish, is the scope and quality of a journal; open access is often not factored into this process, as authors tend to assume this option would be offered by default.

ABOUT RESEARCH CONSULTING

WHO WE ARE

Research Consulting is a leading research and scholarly communication consultancy, combining a breadth of expertise with depth of insight into supporting stakeholders in the global research enterprise.

We work with national and international organisations to help them make the most of their research processes and findings.

We are active participants in the research ecosystem and our work covers all aspects of the research life-cycle - including policy, funding, management, publishing and scholarly communication.

OUR EXPERIENCE

Research Consulting has delivered nearly 200 projects for universities, publishers and vendors, higher education sector bodies, public bodies and higher education funding bodies.

We have a clear understanding of the research landscape and of the needs of its many players. We are familiar with the specific interests and requirements of a wide range of stakeholder groups relevant to publishers as clients or end users.

We have an extensive network in higher education and research and can utilise a range of expert associates. We can reach virtually any relevant stakeholder group to have detailed, in-depth and insightful conversations.

WHAT DO OUR CLIENTS SAY?

"Research Consulting are people who listen; who ensure they understand; who know what's possible and what's not possible; who collect data - the right amount - and take pains to interpret it correctly."

Hamish Macandrew, Chief Operating Officer, ARMA UK

"The team did a great job in helping us frame the project. They then ran things professionally and efficiently, with clear communication and milestones. They were a joy to work with, and the outputs were compelling and useful. I would definitely look to work with them again on similar projects."

Shelley Allen, Head of Open Research, Emerald Publishing

"Research Consulting's expertise is complemented by being approachable and easy to work with. They generally will suggest improvements to a project but without risk of over-complication. And vitally, their reporting is always oriented towards applicability."

Dan Penny, Head of Market Intelligence: Researchers and Audience, Springer Nature

"Research Consulting brought significant rigour to the delivery of a challenging project and their reporting outputs are excellent."

Michael Peak, Senior Adviser, Education Research, British Council

"Research Consulting delivered a wide-ranging project for the University of Oxford, engaging multiple University functions and Oxford's academic community. I was impressed with their responsiveness to our needs and their work has laid a firm foundation for the strategic and operational development of research data management at the University."

Professor Patrick Grant, Pro-Vice-Chancellor (Research), University of Oxford

WOULD YOU LIKE TO KNOW MORE?

Research Consulting has unmatched expertise and deep knowledge of all aspects of the research process. We are experienced at delivering qualitative and mixed-methods research projects and we would welcome the chance to discuss your requirements.

To find out more, please get in touch:

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